

**PEDAGOGICAL ASPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF CRITICAL THINKING OF
HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTE'S STUDENTS**

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Annotatsiya. *Bugungi kunda har bir shaxs dunyoni anglashi, hayot va jamiyat qonuniyatlarini har tomonlama idrok etishi, yer yuzidagi turli xalqlar va millatlar dunyoqarashi, g'oyasi, maslak-muddaolarini bilish uchun ham tanqidiy fikr yurita olishi davr talabi bo'lmoqda. Nega deganda, bugungi zamonda har qanday raqib va muxolif bilan bahsga kirishishi uchun har bir inson tanqidiy fikr olishi zarur.*

Tayanch so'zlar: *pedagogika, fikrlash, tanqidiy fikrlash, talaba, ta'lim dalil, qobiliyat, tarbiya.*

**ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИЕ АСПЕКТЫ РАЗВИТИЯ КРИТИЧЕСКОГО
МЫШЛЕНИЯ УЧАЩИХСЯ ВЫСШИХ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЙ.**

Аннотация. *Сегодня требуется время, чтобы каждый человек осознавал мир, всесторонне воспринимал законы жизни и общества, мог критически мыслить, знать мировоззрения, идеи, нравы разных народов и народностей на земле. Потому что, чтобы вступить в спор с любым противником и оппонентом в наши дни, необходимо, чтобы каждый мог мыслить критически.*

Ключевые слова: *педагогика, мышление, критическое мышление, ученик, образование, доказательство, способность, воспитание.*

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Abstract. *Today it takes time for everyone to realize the world, comprehensively perceive the laws of life and society, be able to think critically, know the worldviews, ideas, mores of different peoples and nationalities on earth. Because in order to enter into an argument with any opponent and opponent nowadays, it is necessary that everyone can think critically.*

Keywords: *pedagogy, thinking, critical thinking, student, education, proof, ability, upbringing.*

The term of "critical thinking" is widely used in pedagogy, social and daily life. Criticism is one of the most important abilities of a person, it protects him from the consequences of mistakes and mistakes. critical thinking is the ability of a person to understand his own point of view on this or that issue, to find new ideas, to analyze events and evaluate them, to think carefully about any judgment or action, is the ability to apply the alleged decisions [1,141 pages].

The main task of an adult educator is to develop critical thinking (reflex ocritica) of students [2, 44 pages].

According to I. Sidney Resnick [3, 519 pages], "Students develop knowledge and creative thinking only if they can apply their knowledge to solve specific problems".

Developing critical thinking is not something that can be taught at a certain age and forgotten. There are no clear paths to critical thinking. Moreover, there is a certain set of educational conditions, with the help of which it is possible to naturalize critical thinkers.

Needless to say, reflection describes a person's self-awareness, his understanding of the basis of his actions and actions. Reflection is the principle of human thinking, which directs it to the

understanding of personal forms and conditions, examining the analysis itself, critically analyzing its content and methods of knowledge, revealing the uniqueness and internal structure of the human spiritual world. The activity of giving self-knowledge is listed [4,155 pages].

The elements of critical thinking include:

- critical thinking
- this is independent thinking;
- information
- the beginning of critical thinking;
- critical thinking begins with identifying the problem that needs to be asked and solved;
- critical thinking leads to reliable evidence;
- critical thinking is social thinking.

First, critical thinking is independent thinking. Since the training is based on the principles of critical thinking, each participant will have his own idea, assessment and belief, excluding others. We can think like that only for ourselves. So, thinking can be called critical thinking only when it has a singular character. Students should have the freedom to think, think, and find answers to even the most complex questions by themselves. Each student decides for himself how to think. Thus, independence is one of the most important aspects of critical thinking. Secondly, information is not the result of critical thinking, but its beginning. Vilim is considered to be a motive that encourages a person to think critically. It is also said that “it is difficult to think with an empty head”. In order to create a complex idea, it is necessary to process a lot of “raw materials” - evidence, ideas, texts, theories, data, concepts. Critical thinking is possible at any age: not only students, but even first graders have life experience and knowledge. As a result of education, children's thinking abilities are improving. Even very young children have the ability to think critically and think completely independently. It is precisely because of critical thinking that the normal cognitive process acquires individuality and understanding, organicity and empathy. Third, critical thinking begins with identifying the problem that needs to be asked and solved. Humanity is curious by nature. When we notice something new, we definitely want to know its essence. Curiosity is an integral feature of any living being [5, 41 pages].

According to the American philosopher and pedagogue J. Dewey, only if students start to deal with a specific problem, they will develop critical thinking. “The starting point of the educational process is considered the most important question related to a certain situation or event is the question that means what kind of problem this event creates”. Only when he is struggling with a specific problem and looking for his own way out of a difficult situation, does he really think. It can be concluded that, while preparing for the lesson, the teacher should determine the range of problems that the students may encounter, and then prepare the students to formulate these problems in their own independent way. Learning through critical thinking turns from the old “school” work into a purposeful, meaningful activity, and during this activity, students do real mental work and solve real life problems. They collect evidence, analyze texts, compare equally strong points of view, and use the opportunities of the team to search for and find answers to the questions they are interested in. Fourth, critical thinking leads to reliable evidence. A critical thinker finds his own personal solution to a problem and supports this decision with rational, reasonable arguments. He admits that other decisions are possible, but he tries to prove that the decision he chose is the most logical and reasonable. Any reliable evidence consists of three main parts. Assertion is considered the center of the argument, its content (sometimes it is called a thesis, main idea or rule).

Confirmation is supported by several evidences. Each of the arguments is strengthened by evidence. Statistical data, a piece of text, personal experience, in general, all ideas that help to prove this reliable evidence and can be recognized by other participants of the discussion can be used as evidence. All the above-mentioned parts of reliable evidence are based on confirmation, evidence and proof, which is the fourth part of it. A premise is the starting point of some kind of guiding account that is common to both the speaker and the writer and his followers, and is considered the basis of all reliable evidence. Reliable evidence is gained only if the existence of counter-evidence, their exaggeration, or the possibility of acceptance is also taken into account. Acknowledgment of different points of view increases the impact of reliable evidence. A critical thinker, armed with very strong evidence, can counter even an opinion with great authority, and it is practically impossible to change such a person's opinion. Moreover, critical thinking is considered social (every human being is a social organism). Any thought can be transmitted only if it is shared with others, or as the philosopher Hannah Arendt wrote: “being with someone makes me whole” [50].

When we debate, read, participate in discussions, protest, exchange ideas with others, we clarify our point of view and deepen it. That is why pedagogues working in the direction of critical thinking try to use different forms of working in pairs or groups in their classes, to effectively use debates and discussions, and to use different ways of showing students' written works. In general, any critical thinker works with a team and solves tasks in a much broader sense than just constructing his own personality. Therefore, a teacher who works in the direction of critical thinking pays more attention to the formation of qualities necessary for effective exchange of ideas, such as: self-restraint, learning to listen to others, responsibility for one's own opinion. Thus, these teachers manage to bring the learning process closer to the real life outside the classroom.

The following ideas can be cited as evidence of critical thinking:

1. Effective continuous education applied to new situations creates a problem for us to understand information and ideas. Students can achieve the highest results only when they actively absorb information and ideas.
2. The learning process will be more successful only when various strategies (forms) of development of thinking activity are used. Such strategies ensure that the educational process becomes more conscious.
3. Only when students can apply their knowledge in solving specific problems, they develop knowledge and creative thinking.
4. Learning based on students' prior knowledge and experience will be solid. All of them give the student the opportunity to connect new information with those who already know.
5. Critical thinking and reading will only work if teachers understand the nuances of ideas and experiences. If the spirit of “only one answer” prevails, then critical thinking will not be possible [80].

Critical thinking is more evident in writing. It will be possible to observe the thought processes in the writing, and this will also create convenience for the teacher. A student who writes is always active. He always thinks independently and uses all the knowledge he has. He lists enough reliable evidence to support his opinion. In addition, it will have a social character by its nature. Because the letter writer writes for the reader. The most valuable thing for a student is that the teacher is interested in his work and treats him with respect, he has the opportunity to share his thoughts with classmates, other teachers, parents and even strangers. Therefore, writing can be considered the most important means of critical thinking.

REFERENCES

1. To‘xtasinov D.F. 5-9-sinf o‘quvchilarining mantiqiy tafakkurini rivojlantirish texnologiyasi. Pedagogika yo‘nalishi bo‘yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) ilmiy darajasini olish uchun yozilgan dissertatsiya. Toshkent – 2020 yil. 141 b.
2. Global Curriculum for Adult Learning & Education. Authors (2nd Edition): Maja Avramovska, Tania Czerwinski, Susanne Lattke. Published by: Institut für Internationale Zusammenarbeit des Deutschen Volkshochschul-Verbandes e. V. (DVV International) Obere Wilhelmstraße 32, 53225 Bonn Federal Republic of Germany. ISBN 978-3-942755-24-5. 44 p.
3. Resnick, Sidney I. A probability path I Sidney Resnick. p. em. Includes bibliographical references and index. ISBN 0-8176-4055-X (hardcover : alk. paper). I. Probabilities. I. Title. QA273.R437 1998. 519' .24--dc21
4. Otajonov J.M. Bo‘lajak boshlang‘ich sinf o‘qituvchilarida reflektiv ko‘nikmalarni rivojlantirish. Pedagogika fanlari bo‘yicha falsafa doktori (PhD) ilmiy darajasini olish uchun tayyorlangan dissertatsiya. Toshkent 2020. 155 b.
5. University Sacramento 4 I Meyers C (1986) Teaching Students to Think Criticallu: A Guide for Fakultu in All Disciplines San Francisco: Jossey-Bass. C.41)